

2021 PROGRAMME PALAU MACAYA

MARCH - JUNE

SEX AND GENDER BIAS IN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND HEALTH

SERIES 2021
PALAU MACAYA

INDEX

- 01** Introduction
- 02** Executive Summary
- 03** Project
Definition
Objectives
Results
Future Actions
- 04** Annex
Dissemination
Programme
Speakers, Participants, Team
Bibliography

01 INTRODUCTION

The entire and equal participation of women in all areas of society is a fundamental Human Right. Despite this, women are still considerably underrepresented in different cultural, political and scientific spheres at various levels (United Nations, 2020). In the scientific community, the participation of women is a key factor to guarantee the efficiency and quality of research. Currently, according to data published by the United Nations, less than 30% of the world's researchers in the areas of science, technology, engineering and mathematics are women (UNESCO, 2019). This inequality in professional participation is reproduced at different levels. Women face biases and barriers in posting, funding, and hiring, as well as in promotion to higher positions, recognition, and visibility of their work compared with men (Grogan, 2019). That is why international and national institutions work to develop and implement measures to promote gender equity. The objective is to contribute decisively to a change the social, scientific and political paradigm. The implementation of public policies, affirmative actions and legislation will allow girls and women to achieve effective participation in the workforce and have the same leadership opportunities in society.

As Schiebinger mentions (Schiebinger & Schraudner, 2011), it is necessary to define a new structure at three levels: 1) fixing the numbers in relation to participation, with the goal of increasing the proportion of women researchers in science and having a representative balance of social diversity; 2) fixing the institutions, and programs that consider the relevance of gender equality, review of policies and affirmative actions; and 3) fixing the knowledge. It is mainly this aspect that the Bioinfo4Women (B4W) programme focuses on. Not only is there an inequality in the participation of women in science, but data, technologies and designs have a standard focus for the entire population that is not inclusive. In such a way, it is imperative to reformulate research, work methods, tests, and procedures, to include the sex and gender perspective in scientific research. This process requires deep interdisciplinary collaborations between experts in gender, education, science, medicine, and engineering.

Within this framework, the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) has developed the B4W program, a non-profit initiative of the Life Sciences Department that began its activities in 2018. The program works on different axes, with actions and research that promote change in the scientific area. On one hand, it seeks to promote and increase the space of women researchers in computational biology with special emphasis on high professional positions and the transition to them. It supports women researchers in computational biology by promoting the exchange of knowledge and experiences of outstanding women researchers through activities such as seminars, conferences, training opportunities, and mentoring. Additionally, it seeks to give a greater visibility to the contribution of

women researchers in different fields of biology, with a particular focus on the areas of personalised medicine, bioinformatics, and high-performance computing (HPC). On the other hand, it promotes research on the analysis of sex and gender biases in computational biology and applications of artificial intelligence for personalized medicine and scientific practice. Finally, at the regional, national and international institutional level, the B4W aims to build a more collaborative, supportive and egalitarian scientific community that benefits society as a whole.

The Programme has the institutional support of the Life Sciences Department of the BSC and contributes to the fulfilment of the centre's objective of promoting the development of a scientific career in accordance with the gender equality plan developed.

OBJETIVOS DE DESARROLLO SOSTENIBLE

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS. UNITED NATIONS.
<https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/sustainable-development-goals/>

The objectives of the project were designed in relation to the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (Sustainable Development Goals and Goals - Sustainable Development, n.d.), specifically goal 3 of Health and Well-being; Goal 5 Gender equality and Goal 10 Reduction of inequalities. In 2020, the B4W proposed the project "Sex and Gender Biases in Health and Artificial Intelligence" in accordance with the objectives of the La Caixa Foundation, to provide a framework for reflection and thought on issues, and social problems that impact the population. Thus, during the year 2021, the program started a unique conference series, in which specialists from different regions (geographic) and fields (of knowledge, expertise) have collaborated with the common objective of raising awareness of the problem of sex and gender biases in health and artificial intelligence.

02 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Within the framework of the 5th La Caixa Foundation Call, the project "Sex and Gender Bias in Artificial Intelligence and Health" has been developed, organized by the B4W of the BSC with La Caixa Foundation.

This conference series has been carried out over four months, starting on March 16th, 2021, and ending on June 16th 2021. During this period, the following events have been organized:

- Conferences given by experts in the area,
- Seminars with open debate between specialists and citizens,
- Workshops with different social groups to define lines of action.

The objectives determined in the project were: a. Provide a space for open debate between scientists and society on sex and gender bias in science and technology; b. Promote an international network of professional women in the area; c. Elaborate consensual strategies; and d. Disseminate the results of the series.

The conference series started with an opening session on March 16th, 2021, where members of the B4W presented the programme, agenda and objectives. The event counted with contributed talks from public institutions as well as from recognized researchers in the area. The two following sessions held in April and May tackled the problem of sex and gender bias from two perspectives: personalized medicine and artificial intelligence. The topics were debated and the space for reflection was assured by a seminar open to the public, with a subsequent closed workshop with invited specialists on the subject

The methodology applied in the workshops was mainly based on Design Thinking (McLaughlin, J.E et al; 2019) a technique used to innovate and focus on the needs of people. The process considers both the socio-ethical and the technological aspects and ensures that the proposed solutions are viable and sustainable.

DESIGN THINKING METHODOLOGY. STANFORD UNIVERSITY.
<https://dschool.stanford.edu/>

As a result of the actions, conferences, seminars and workshops, the Bioinfo4Women program systematized a series of outcomes and future proposals to develop and guide the work. On June 16th the conference series closed with a session summarizing the main conclusions that emerged from the activities. This report provides detailed information on each part. We summarize the actions in 9 points as the main conclusions to continue working.

Conclusions

1. Public policies and Regulations
2. Education and Training
3. Social Dialogue and Communication: Awareness
4. Algorithmic Audits and Guidelines
5. Inclusive Strategies in Healthcare and Bio-medical Research
6. Quality and Fairness: Representativeness
7. Multidisciplinary and Inclusive Teams
8. Social & Ethical Impact IA
9. Trustworthy IA

03 PROJECT

DEFINITION

The Bioinfo4Women programme of the Life Sciences Department of the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) coordinated the series following this process. The series is structured on two main themes: (1) personalised medicine and (2) artificial intelligence. Each theme included different activities: seminar, working group and participatory workshop. The goal of these activities was to allow and encourage discussion between scientists and prominent representatives from different fields (business, media, NGOs, research institutes and public administration, among others) and to raise awareness of sex and gender bias in health and the risk of amplifying and perpetuating bias through artificial intelligence. Likewise, it was developed to promote collaboration and debate networks that could contribute to knowledge generation, such as the publication of scientific articles on the topic, and to inspire, promote and apply to research projects with a social impact.

OBJECTIVE

The objective of the series was to raise awareness in the society and the scientific community of the implications of sex and gender biases in the development and applications of new technologies in the field of health and personalised medicine. In particular, the focus was on reviewing the risk of bias amplification and its perpetuation through the application of artificial intelligence.

The main challenge was to create an open debate between the scientific community and society to exchange knowledge and analyse the social, ethical and technological challenges related to the subject, with the aim of identifying and making innovative proposals to address them.

OPENING CONFERENCE

RESULTS

A. OPENING CONFERENCE

The opening conference was held on March 16th, 2021. The welcome to the conference and the participation in the project was given by Barbara Palacio, director of the Palau Macaya from La Caixa Foundation. The structure of the session together with the presentation of the series and the lines of research were introduced by María José Rementeria and Dr. Nataly Buslón, both members of the B4W of the BSC.

Dr. Zulema Altamirano, director of the Women and Science Unit of the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation, presented the gender perspective in the field of science and innovation, emphasising the area of artificial intelligence and health. For that purpose, she presented the objectives and the four pillars that guide her work: *Evaluate* the current state of the gender gap, to know if the indicators currently implemented are adequate with the equality policies, *Make women visible*, so they can serve as role models for those young women and girls who want to follow their steps. *Transform environments and institutions* where there are still gender biases. For this reason, it is imperative to work for a diverse, egalitarian and safe environment. *Promote, enhance and accelerate* these changes.

To conclude, Altamirano highlighted three main challenges: *1. Attract female talent, 2. Retain and develop opportunities to empower women researchers in the scientific field and 3. Integrate the gender dimension in research, development and innovation (R&D + I).*

Challenge 3: Gender dimension in I+D+I

- ✓ Gender dimension in **all phases of research projects** is key for **excellence**
- ✓ **More awareness, capacity building and gender expertise** is needed in research team to adequately integrate the gender perspective.

11

Laura Pérez Castaño

Zulema Altamirano I+D+I (MCIA)

OPENING CONFERENCE, 2021. PALAU MACAYA, BARCELONA.

The following speaker, Laura Pérez Castaño, Deputy Mayor for Social Rights, Global Justice, Feminism and LGTBI at the Barcelona City Council, detailed the work

carried out by different institutions in Barcelona, emphasising the necessary impulse needed in the field of health. Her presentation explained the importance of identifying gender gaps in the digital environment as a key asset to address it in the health sector. She listed the gender biases that must be overcome and gave examples of the work of municipal services in different public policies and the specific actions they develop based on the use of Artificial Intelligence in the fight against social inequalities.

OPENING CONFERENCE, 2021. PALAU MACAYA, BARCELONA.

The first keynote talk was given by Professor Alfonso Valencia, ICREA Research Professor, director of the Life Sciences Department at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) and director of the Spanish National Bioinformatics Institute (INB-ISCIII). During his presentation, he showed examples of recent scientific research on existing medical differences based on sex, classifying desirable and undesirable biases in relation to the article "Sex and gender differences and biases in artificial intelligence for biomedicine and healthcare" published in [npj Digital Medicine](#) (Cirillo, Catuara-Solarz *et al.*, 2020) and indicating some technical solutions to address them.

The accent was made on the urgent need for gender-balanced clinical trials in health and, specifically, an adequate data annotation as well as a gender- and sex-aware labelling process to improve the adherence of biomedical resources to the FAIR -Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable- principles (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016).

The second keynote talk was given by Dr. Maria Teresa Ferretti, co-founder and scientific director of the Women's Brain Project (WBP). Dr. Ferretti referred to the joint research efforts involving both the BSC and the WBP and her research in mental health with the perspective of sex and gender in personalised medicine. She elucidated the key relevance of considering sex differences in disease incidence, treatment, and admission to intensive care units during the COVID-19 pandemic (Arnegard *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, she illustrated the importance of considering the socioeconomic and cultural factors in healthcare interventions. The inclusion of sex and gender characteristics in biomedical research will allow us to improve precision medicine and AI-based solutions and depression, a topic that is of great importance to the WBP organization.

She also pointed out problems arising from preclinical models that use mostly male mice rather than female mice and that do not stratify the data by sex. Data generation and data analysis that do not account for sex differences in animal models can affect the clinical development of drugs and have a negative impact on population health. Additionally, Dr. Ferretti promoted the uptake of trustworthy and unbiased artificial intelligence by healthcare systems allowing researcher and practitioners to analyse the data and provide insights under the lens of sex and gender differences. A call to action is made to characterize these differences for the analysis of health data, at all levels.

The objective of such a call of action is to jointly seek solutions with the scientific community, industry, technological sector, public policy decision makers and the public. It is necessary to strengthen efforts in the explicability of algorithms, to resolve biases in artificial intelligence systems, to define strategies, and finally to incorporate an ethical review throughout the development of automated systems aimed at the social welfare of the population.

The slide, titled "Our Call to Action", features a vertical list of four light blue rounded rectangular boxes, each containing a specific action item. The items are: 1. "Analysis of sex differences in baseline patients characteristic, progression of the disease, clinical outcomes even when using digital of fluid biomarkers etc." 2. "Awareness of sex and gender differences among the scientific community, pharmaceutical and technology industries, policy makers and the general public" 3. "Implement solutions, such as explainable algorithms in data analysis and drug development to detect bias in the system and implement mitigation strategies" 4. "Incorporate key ethical considerations during every stage of technological development, ensuring that the systems maximize well-being and health of the global population". To the right of the text is a video inset showing a woman, identified as Maria Teresa Ferretti, speaking. The WBP logo is visible in the top right corner of the slide.

OPENING CONFERENCE, 2021. PALAU MACAYA

Thus, the opening conference presents the series, initiating the public debate on the topic and inviting society to participate in the challenges presented.

**FIRST
BLOCK:
PERSONALISED
MEDICINE**

FIRST BLOCK

The first thematic block was focused on health. Personalised medicine proposes a new paradigm in which therapeutic decisions are guided by the individual attributes of each patient. Sufficient scientific evidence has been accumulated supporting the existence of individual differences in the incidence of diseases, their evolution and responses to medications, not only due to genetic factors also biological sex and gender and sociocultural factors. To predict the variability of the therapeutic response, to avoid adverse effects or lack of efficacy of drugs and to determine the prognosis of diseases. Biomedical research must be powered by the consideration of sex and gender differences in relation to all aspects of health research and practise from experimental and technological developments to ethics and legal aspects.

B. PERSONALISED MEDICINE SEMINAR

SEX AND GENDER PERSPECTIVE IN THE FUTURE OF PERSONALIZED MEDICINE

<p>Moderates: Davide Cirillo PostDoctoral Researcher at the Computational Biology group, BSC</p>				
--	---	---	--	---

PERSONALISED MEDICINE SEMINAR, 2021. PALAU MACAYA, BARCELONA.

The open seminar "*The perspective of sex and gender in the future of Personalised Medicine*" was held on April 14th 2021. The development of the session was moderated by Dr. Davide Cirillo, researcher of the Computational Biology group, Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC).

The debate was opened by Dr. Carme Valls Llbet, director of the Women, Health and Quality of Life program at the CAPS Center for Health Analysis and Programs, politician and doctor specialized in endocrinology with a gender perspective. During her presentation, she explained the difference between the characteristics of sex and gender data and the importance of including social, economic, and environmental dimensions in health research.

Then, Dr. Valeria Raparelli, from the University of Alberta in Canada and professor at the University of Ferrara in Italy, highlighted the warning signs related to the integration of sexual and gender factors into personalised medicine, especially in cardiovascular diseases.

The contribution of Professor Luis Rocha, director of the NSF-NRT Complex Networks and Systems graduate programme in computing, member of the Indiana University Network Science Institute and member of the teaching team of the Cognitive Science Program at Indiana University, Bloomington (USA), raised how biases represent a limitation to model systems and how they are propagated in algorithmic solutions, from a theoretical and technical point of view.

Finally, Dr. Silvina Catuara Solarz, specialized in neurobiology, project evaluator and mentor of emerging companies at EIT Health, member of the WHO roster of experts in digital health and director of Application of Technology for Neuroscience and Mental Health of the Women's Brain Project, talked about the importance of having a multilevel knowledge of health and diseases to achieve personalised medicine. In addition, she referred to the ubiquitous nature of sex and gender biases in AI and technologies applied to biomedical research and healthcare applications as well as how to address this challenge.

The debate with experts was driven by thematic axes structured by the BSC team with defined questions on the subject. This open discussion shaped the subsequent workshop.

WORKSHOP: Sex and Gender Biases in Artificial Intelligence and Health: Building a future for equality: challenges and action strategies for personalized medicine

The workshop *"Building a future for equality: challenges and action strategies for personalized medicine"* was held on Wednesday April 14 from 3 to 5:30 p.m. The workshop was held online through Zoom. The format consisted of small multidisciplinary groups that were previously defined to ensure diversity, in areas of research, work, interest, as well as considering the language and geographical area.

The goal of the group participatory workshop was to analyse the application of the gender and sex perspective in scientific research, specifically in health and personalised medicine. We encouraged participants to reflect on tools and strategies to tackle existing biases in health, with the aim of applying innovative solutions to reduce them and improve the quality of life of the population.

The workshop gathered 30 experts (25 women and 5 men). 22 of them had an academic profile, journalists, people linked to NGOs, hospitals, and other institutions. Additionally, 6 people were from the Barcelona Supercomputing Center and there were 2 facilitators from Coemprén. They were all engaged in generating ideas and proposals to build a future with equality strategies in personalised medicine.

To facilitate the debate among the participants, 7 challenges were proposed to focus the conversation. The participants were divided into 4 groups of 5 or 6 people. Each of these groups selected three challenges to discuss, debate and expose the different points of view from their personal perspectives.

CHALLENGES

FALTAN DATOS	1. ¿Cómo podríamos mejorar la falta de datos e información para evitar los sesgos de sexo y género en salud?	1. How might we provide solutions to the lack of data to avoid sex and gender issues?
IA	2. ¿Cómo podemos evitar que los algoritmos de IA en salud no estén sesgados?	2. How can we avoid algorithm (AI) biases?
MAL USO DATOS	3. ¿Qué medidas se podrían poner en marcha para evitar una mala praxis en el uso de los datos? (manipulación de datos, control, exclusión de grupos sociales...)	3. What solutions can be defined to prevent misuse of data? (manipulations, control, exclusion of minorities...)
DESIGUALDAD	4. ¿Qué acciones se podrían potenciar para que la medicina personalizada y la inteligencia artificial eviten las desigualdades sociales (género, ingresos, raza, edad, ...)?	4. What actions could be taken in personalised medicine and AI to avoid social inequalities (in gender, income, race, age...)?
PRIVACIDAD	5. ¿Qué medidas propondrías para garantizar la privacidad del paciente en un sistema medicina personalizada?	5. How might we guarantee patient's data privacy in personalised medicine?
CONCIENCIA	6. ¿Como podríamos concienciar al <grupo de interés> sobre la importancia del sesgo de sexo y género en salud?	6. How might we make a given <target group> more aware of the importance of sex&gender biases?
DIVULGACIÓN	7. ¿Cuáles son las mejores formas de difundir la problemática para combatir el sesgo de sexo y género en salud?	7. How might we best disseminate these issues to beat sex&gender biases in health?

PERSONALISED MEDICINE WORKSHOP, 2021. PALAU MACAYA, BARCELONA.

By analysing the results of the workshop, the following topics developed by the participants emerged:

Challenge A. Lack of Data. How can we provide solutions to tackle the lack of data and its consequences on sex and gender issues? Two of the participating groups discussed the problem related to the lack of data and the quality of data to feed the AI models. The proposed ideas were based on:

Guidelines and Recommendations by the main approval associations such as Spanish Agency of Medicines and Medical Products (AEMPS), European Medicines Agency (EMA) and The European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and

Associations (EFPIA) including the category of sex and gender in the data collection forms. The need for a consensus in the definition of sex and gender used in scientific studies was also discussed. In particular, the terms sex and gender must be used appropriately and consistently in the different databases and information repositories.

Expansion of Data Collection by diversifying the sources, including health data from primary care and population data from schools and institutes as well as from neighbourhood associations. It was proposed to launch voluntary campaigns to collect inclusive data, to incorporate into repositories reflecting as much population variability as possible. Moreover, there was a debate on how to consider gender outside the binary system.

Data quality: Evaluation and Inclusion Criteria. The need to include data evaluation criteria in the policies of scientific journals for the publication of articles was discussed. A necessity of checking the quality, completeness and balance regarding sex and gender of the data used in the research.

Challenge B. Biases in AI algorithms. How can we prevent AI algorithms for health from being biased? Two of the participating groups debated the problem related to the biases of AI algorithms used in health and the ways to address them. Ideas were proposed based on:

Multidisciplinary and inclusive development teams. The need to demystify AI and to propose systems that provide unbiased answers to scientific questions and hypotheses was debated. It was considered essential that people are part of all the phases of AI development: the ideation of the approach, the implementation of the system and verification of the results (human-in-the-loop), and the adoption of multidisciplinary and inclusive development teams.

AI Models / Algorithms. A demand emerged to review the basic characteristics of the AI models to avoid unfair classifications, as well as the need to promote explainable and transparent AI to interpret possible contradictions in the results and allow identifying possible biases in them. We also identified a general concern regarding data anonymisation and reidentification, as this is particularly critical in the health sector where personal and sensible data are used to train AI models.

Quality and fairness in training data sets. Participants discussed about the need of training data sets that not only have the necessary quality, but also ensure that they are balanced as a whole in accordance with the variables of interest of the problem addressed. Concerns were also raised on the necessity to adjust to the population distribution avoiding over adjustments to a subset of the population. Finally, participants proposed to have a catalogue of biases that allows developers to easily identify them.

Control and Correction Tools. The discussion focused on the creation of teams to develop metrics to evaluate the models, techniques for mitigating biases in the models, such as loss functions for unbalanced data, and tools for measuring biases in the data, as well as methods to be able to increase the data in case of unbalanced data sets.

Challenge C. Inequalities. What actions could be promoted so that personalised medicine and artificial intelligence avoid social inequalities of gender, income, race and age? Two of the participating groups debated the problems related to inequalities that personalised medicine and AI can produce. Ideas were proposed based on:

Definition of inclusive strategies in health promotion and care. Participants highlighted the need to include the gender perspective in all the strategies that are defined to promote people's health. This encompasses defining inclusive strategies promoting adequate care for people from vulnerable groups such as LGBTIQ+, with special attention to transgender people.

Consider and include intersectional groups in medical research. Participants discussed the need to expand and include intersectional categories in medical research, such as sex, gender, sexual orientation, ethnicity, place of residence, socio-economic situation, disability, age. It is essential to provide the adequate representation of population segments generally underrepresented in clinical studies, in particular for those that receive public funding for their conduct.

Review and correct the lack of data in medical studies, completing them with sociocultural data from various sources. The need to balance the lack of data of those groups that present an inadequate weight in the data sets was debated, using sociocultural data as possible sources of information to be integrated. The promotion of sociological studies and the integration of their results with health data was endorsed.

Challenge C. Consciousness. How could we make the group of interest aware of the importance of sex and gender bias in health? Three of the participating groups debated issues related to raising awareness of the problem among different stakeholders such as biomedical researchers, physicians, companies, laboratories, technologists, and the public. Ideas were proposed based on:

Public policies. Political actors should look for synergies with people from the industrial and academic world to develop guidelines and promote the financing of research projects on sex and gender differences in health, promoting prizes for this type of studies. Such collaborations should also include training on the subject for public personalities with responsibilities and decision-making and financing capacity.

Education and training. The need to adapt university programmes to include the problem of biases, particularly in degrees related to health and engineering, was discussed to make future professionals aware of the risks and their impact. It was also proposed to promote education and awareness of sex and gender biases in schools and institutes, through scientific talks and educational campaigns to promote children education in equality.

Awareness and Dissemination. Proposals for conducting awareness and dissemination campaigns were analysed, pointing out the influence of biases in data repositories and the adverse consequences of inequality, as well as alternatives to reduce the gap. It was recommended to develop outreach campaigns in schools for parents and cultural associations including groups and social movements, as well as influencers, to reach a wider audience. Scientific documentaries showing the relevance of historical events in discriminatory clinical practice were also suggested.

Regarding awareness in the clinical part. It was proposed to disseminate information related to sex and gender differences in symptoms of diseases for a better diagnosis (for example, heart attacks) and treatments. It is essential to promote activism from scientific circles and the dissemination of international campaigns through social networks and the media on the danger of biases and the value of the sex and gender-specific diagnosis.

Challenge D. Dissemination. What are the best ways to combat sex and gender bias in health? Three of the participating groups discussed the different ways and means to disseminate information and combat existing biases. Ideas were proposed based on:

Scientific communication. The scientific community can play a key role in the digital transformation of our society by contributing to the digital literacy of citizens through, for instance, multidisciplinary online seminars. Moreover, they should also disseminate in different phases of educational primary, secondary and university degrees and doctoral courses.

Advertising and Campaigns. Participants suggested to involve popular streaming channels such as Netflix or to collaborate with influencers and women leaders to engage the general audience into the knowledge of AI technologies, its capabilities, impacts and limitations. Other proposals included the design of board games, TV series led by women.

Finally, the best ideas of the workshop were summarised:

- Include the sex and gender variables into all clinical trials, not only at the level of data collection but also in the downstream analyses.

- Include disaggregated data including gender and sex diversity (intersectionality), starting from the initial collection process, and include the sex variable in the pre-clinical phase.
- Implement specialised training for clinical professionals and health researchers starting from the beginning of their careers, and generate curricular programs that are included in formal academic education from an early stage and further in research (not only for health personnel).
- Collect sex and gender data when people download a health app or sign up for a newsletter to obtain more information.
- Incorporate data from institutions and organizations accessible to groups at risk of social exclusion (social work, NGOs, etc.)
- Devise media campaigns informing about the problem of sex and gender in clinical practice and dissemination.
- Advocate for the defence of the inclusion of data and diversity at the political and public level.
- Increase funding to address the problem and enhance the gender and sex perspective in science.
- Include sex and gender balance as a mandatory requirement for project funding and research.
- Write job offers with inclusive language to encourage women and diversity groups to apply.
- Best practices and characterization of the dataset *before, during and after* the development of an AI algorithm and promote impact audit on such systems.

**SECOND
BLOCK:
ARTIFICIAL
INTELLIGENCE**

SECOND BLOCK

The second block of the series focused on artificial intelligence to address the risks and problems present in terms of sex and gender bias. AI bias is present in algorithms in different ways, from the design of the experiment and the data collected and used to train the algorithm to finally interpret the outcomes. As a result, it can generate unfair decisions, leading to discrimination or stigmatisation towards certain groups of people. Some of these biases are inherited from historical or socially constructed biases. AI can help identify and reduce these biases, but it can also increase the problem of inclusion and diversity if they are not embedded throughout the AI system lifecycle. An open and multidisciplinary dialogue is needed to include a gender and sex perspective in the design and deployment of AI in healthcare, to promote fairness and trustworthiness in society.

C. SEMINAR AI

kw bioinfo 4women

PROYECTO SELECCIONADO **CONVOCATORIA PALAU MACAYA** #AIGenderBias

Social, Ethical and Technical Challenges of Sex and Gender Bias in AI and Healthcare

<p>Modera: Atia Cortés. Postdoctoral Researcher Social Link Analytics, BSC</p>				
--	---	--	---	---

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE SEMINAR, 2021. PALAU MACAYA, BARCELONA.

The open seminar *"Social, Ethical and Technical challenges of sex and gender bias in AI and healthcare"* was held on May 11th, 2021. The session was moderated by Dr. Àtia Cortés, researcher at the Social Link Analytics unit, Barcelona Supercomputing Center.

During the debate, Dr. Karina Gibert, professor at the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, co-founder and director of the IDEAI-UPC group and vice president of Equity and Ethics at COEINF, began the session with her presentation on the analysis of the ethical and technical aspects, as well as the challenges of gender and sex in health through the use of artificial intelligence. She introduced examples of bias at different levels of the lifecycle of an AI system and presented the ethical

requirements for a Trustworthy AI proposed by the High-Level Expert Group on AI from the European Commission.

Dr. Itziar de Lecuona, associate professor at the University of Barcelona School of Medicine and deputy director of the Bioethics and Law Observatory; Chair of Bioethics by UNESCO, talked about research in responsible innovation and the perspective of ethics and philosophy of law. She reviewed different examples of change and new challenges that we have to face. She presented the *"Guidelines for reviewing health research and innovation projects that use emergent technologies and personal data"*, referring to the document published at the University of Barcelona (Lecuona, 2019)

Subsequently, Dr. Allison Gardner from Keele University, representative of Women Leading in AI and member of the IEEE Standard Association, gave a key European framework for the research, highlighting the use of machine learning to predict diseases, in relation to sex and gender and computing capacity, ethical aspects and relevance of the governance of artificial intelligence. In this regard, she mentioned the existence of more than 85 ethical principles and frameworks of AI. She emphasised the fact that most of them have been designed by white men, which is by itself a bias to review (*Principled Artificial Intelligence* | Berkman Klein Center, 2020)

ETHICAL AI PRINCIPLES AND FRAMEWORKS

#1 Human Agency and Oversight	#2 Technical Robustness and Safety	#3 Privacy and Data Governance	#4 Transparency	#5 Diversity, Non-discrimination and Fairness	#6 Societal and Environmental Well-being	#7 Accountability
Human Agency and Oversight	Resilience to Abuse and Security	Privacy	Traceability	Avoidance of Unfair Bias	Environmental Well-being	Audibility
Human Oversight	General Safety	Data Governance	Explicability	Accountability and Remedial Design	Impact on Work and Study	Risk Management
	Accuracy		Communication	Stakeholder Participation	Impact on Society and Legal or Ethical Norms	
	Reliability, Robustness and Interoperability					

Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment

ASSESSMENT LIST FOR TRUSTWORTHY AI: ALTAI

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE SEMINAR, 2021. PALAU MACAYA, BARCELONA.

Finally, Dr. Paula Petrone, Associate Research Professor at ISGlobal and Founder and CEO at Phenobyte, described her experience as a data science advisor for pharmaceutical companies and biotech start-ups, outlining the need for real-world evidence analysis based on patient data to understand human diseases and make efficient drug development for each patient. She explained that today the data is poor, based on a publication in *The Lancet Digital Health* 2021 (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2021) pointed out the main obstacles in ethnicity and skin colour, sex and gender,

socioeconomic status, location, and age in medical care. She highlighted that today's data is unregulated, which drives and reinforces inequalities. Therefore, she stressed the need to demand more transparency and more diverse teams to change the current situation.

■ **Desafíos sociales, éticos y tecnológicos del sesgo de sexo y género en la IA y la atención médica**

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE SEMINAR, 2021. PALAU MACAYA, BARCELONA.

During the session, discussion lines were defined, structured by the BSC team, with a set of questions about the theme to debate that allowed us to think and address the problem. In this way this seminar casted the following working time for the participative group workshop.

D. Workshop 2. GENDER BIAS IN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND HEALTH: Building a Future

The workshop “Building a future for equality: a route map to an inclusive AI for a better health system” was on Thursday May the 11th from 3 to 5.30pm. It was held in a virtual conference, working with small multidisciplinary groups that were previously selected to define a working system that guaranteed diversity in research, working and interest areas as well as considering the language and geographic location.

The objective of the participative workshop was the scientific analysis over the sex and gender bias in the new technologies and artificial intelligence, and the risk of its existing amplification and consolidation. Therefore, we aimed to define improvement strategies and possible solutions addressing the problem from a

different and inclusive point of view over the social, ethic and technological challenges.

The workshop had 28 participants (23 women and 5 men) from diverse areas (academic, journalism, NGO linked, health worker, and other institutions) related to the subject and with an interest to generate new ideas and proposals to build a future with equality strategies in the use of artificial intelligence in health. To complete the activity, five members of the B4W program were present as observers, as well as 2 facilitators.

To facilitate the debate between participants, seven challenges were raised at the beginning of the workshop to focus the conversation. The participants were divided into 4 groups of 5 to 6 persons. Each one of those groups selected three challenges to discuss, debate and expose the diverse points of view from their perspective.

CHALLENGES			
Regulación IA	¿Qué aspectos deberían regularse para conseguir una IA confiable/sin sesgo?	What aspects should be regulated to achieve a reliable/not biased IA?	AI Regulations
Evitar sesgos en IA	¿Qué aspectos deberían regularse para conseguir una IA confiable/sin sesgo?	How can bias be avoided (either in data, algorithms, interpretation)?	Avoid AI biases
Impacto social positivo IA Salud	¿Cómo podemos garantizar que la IA en salud tenga un impacto social positivo alineado con los SDGs (sustainable development goals)?	How can we guarantee that IA in health has a positive impact aligned with SDGs (sustainable development goals)?	Positive social impact of AI in health
Métodos evaluación medicina personalizada IA	¿Qué métodos de evaluación ayudarían a generar confianza en la medicina personalizada basada en IA?	What evaluation methods would help generate confidence in personalized medicine based in AI?	Evaluation methods in AI personalized medicine
Conciencia	¿Qué acciones prácticas son necesarias para concienciar a los diferentes grupos de interés de sus derechos y responsabilidades en uso de la IA? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ciudadanía • Investigadores en biomedicina, médicos, ... • Empresas, laboratorios, tecnólogos, ... • Gobierno 	What practical actions are needed to promote consciousness to different stakeholders about their rights and responsibilities in the use of AI? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Citizens * Researchers in biomedicine, physicians.. * Companies, labs, technologist... 	Consciousness

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE WORKSHOP, 2021. PALAU MACAYA, BARCELONA.

From the analysis of the results of the workshop the topics that were developed by the participants can be grouped into the following categories:

Challenge A. AI Regulation: Which aspects should be regulated to achieve a trusted AI without risks? The challenge was boarded by two teams establishing ideas of implementing:

Algorithms Auditing. It was proposed to establish auditing systems in algorithms so that the data is complete, representative of the population and not biased. It was deemed as imperative to make controls in AI systems to avoid discrimination, prejudices, and a negative impact in society. Moreover, it was mentioned the necessity to develop further the analysis of explainability and transparency of operations.

Certification and Regulation. The legal aspect is a key point that was debated in the workshop, highlighting the importance of having a strong legal scheme, a normative development linked to the article 9.2 i of the GDPR (The General Data Protection Regulation) and the posterior application of the regulation. It was proposed to work on the inclusion of citizens from analysed collectives in the regulatory process. In addition, it should be mandatory to show a release of responsibility over the rights and risks that the deployment of the AI application has over the population. Moreover, the regulation should require that the design of AI systems include the perspectives of sex, gender, age, ethnicity and other aspects regarding minorities as part of the analysis.

It was also proposed to define a control in the datasets, in their design and their creation. Finally, it was remarked on the necessity of open data policies that guarantee over the ensemble of shared data and the interchange protocols of information.

Inclusion of socio-cultural aspects. Social Impact. An aspect which was mentioned several times in the AI regulation challenge was the relation to the SDG (Sustainable Development Goals) for the evaluation of the impact. It is essential to establish general norms that have a global perspective of the universal necessities and challenges. Moreover, it is time to consider the socio-cultural challenges, connecting with the population and creating literacy about opportunities, limitations and risks that AI has in society.

Challenge B. Avoid AI Bias: Which aspects should be regulated to achieve a trusted AI without risks? Two teams worked on challenge B and presented the following conclusions.

Quality and balance in Datasets. Participants discussed the importance of identifying bias in training data to improve the quality and explicability of the results. The process involved collecting data without bias, defining the conditions of reusing the data, investing resources to balance the whole data, its quality and its representativeness, as well as defining relevant organisational, technical and security measures.

Discussions were also conveyed around the importance of having certificates and recognitions of fair AI, data sheets and quality labels for datasets, and certifications

that guarantee processes. This implies a framework development and enabling the accessibility, curation and its availability for developers.

All this process will allow developers to design AI architectures based on a dataset that is not deliberately biased. It was debated about the necessity of creating a new life cycle diagram of AI and Data Science that includes control points for bias, such as verification lists or established guidelines to be followed and tested by AI practitioners.

Inclusive development teams. To work against bias, during the workshop it was mentioned the importance of the bias data contrast with the scientific evidence. To define an indicator tracking system of sex and gender, ethnicity, age and other factors in the development of the projects. To generate balanced and inclusive research teams that represent minorities and enhance teams with diversity.

Regulation. Working on a website similar to expasy for fair AI tools, resources addressed to schools and universities for ethical AI. An example being BEEP (Project of bioethical education). It was proposed to define a certified authority about bias to evaluate a mandatory ethical evaluation of the data before using it to avoid drifting into wrong conclusions.

Communication and Education. It was discussed about promoting awareness, communication, dissemination over present challenges. Educate and train developers over classifying desirable and undesirable biases to be able to avoid negative algorithmic biases. Furthermore, professional associations should mobilize professionals to explain machine learning methods and differentiate the uncontrolled bias over the desired specialization of the systems.

Control tools, Correction and Evaluation. It is important that during the evaluation of research projects financed by big organisations, inclusion of sex and gender perspective is considered and mandatory. Questions remained about the audits. The question of who was in charge of these, institutions or an NGO, etc. And finally, the necessity to develop mandatory and standardised AI tools to detect biases.

Challenge C. AI social impact: How can we guarantee that AI in health will have a positive social impact in line with the SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals by the UN)? From the working groups, two devoted their work to review the social impact in AI, summarizing their ideas in the following:

Consider Social Inequalities and Integrate Citizenship. It was debated the social impacts in society and the risk of not considering the inequalities. On the contrary, it was mentioned that if AI is well implemented, it can democratise access to health and reduce current inequalities. In the same line, it was commented on the positive aspect of the presence of women in STEM and its impact on better and more efficient results.

Align AI towards social objectives and present challenges. The importance of using AI to detect violence and/or domestic abuse, depression, the prediction of malnutrition in vulnerable populations with intelligent systems and applications personalized oriented to social welfare. Also, the integration of heterogeneous data sources (medical, legal, social, environmental) to achieve personalised medicine, in such a way that the quality of data on vulnerable populations and minorities in the sector improves.

Participants commented on the relevance of incorporating medical advisers and patient groups in the projects, to guarantee that useful resources are invested and will be used for the benefit of the patients. As well as to conceive a system where citizens can question the processes, bringing more quality and guarantees to them.

Optimise Resources, Evaluate AI Sustainability, Energy Factor. Participants mentioned the necessity of working on the application of AI to enhance sustainability. It is important to consider the best optimisation in energy consumption, the ecological footprint of Big Data, the energy consumption in the management and use of computation, for big models and the evaluation of the implementation costs. The groups discussed the importance of including the environmental impact aspects of AI. It was also mentioned that those environmental factors (for example, exposome) should be included and analysed in the development of AI for health.

Education. Participants discussed the importance of making the public aware of the use and application of AI, using tools to promote communication, dissemination to educate. The implication of professional associations is essential to develop training on machine learning methods and to differentiate bias. The need to design a global scheme to train scientists in the field of life sciences, computer scientists, commercial managers, law professionals, politicians as well as other professionals was discussed.

Research Quality. As mentioned in other challenges, a relevant aspect is quality. It is necessary to increase the inclusion of different social groups in the design of clinical trials, the development of tools and algorithms debugged, accessible and available. The representativity of the population in that inclusion was also deemed as essential.

Another important aspect mentioned was the importance to influence the financial flow, requiring transparency in trustworthy AI in requests and tenders of funds (Ethical Funding for Trustworthy AI (EFTAI) (Oldfield *et al.*, 2021) ethical funding for a reliable AI framework. It was also proposed that funding calls require diversity groups, transparency of knowledge, innovation and transversal training

with interdisciplinary work, under the participative development that maximise social awareness in AI.

Challenge D. Evaluation Methods: Which evaluation methods could help build trust in personalised medicine based on AI? Three teams analysed the challenge D considering as relevant:

Evaluation, AI Revision, and Auditing. For the groups it was key to think about how to integrate citizens into evaluation systems. The need to fix methodologies for the citizens to participate in the development process of AI, that allows to highlight problems and errors was discussed. Making sure that the dataset is representative of the population, and from this way, evaluations have a complete vision of the AI system. For this, they conclude that it is necessary a project that determines: (1) a literature review of the state of the art; (2) identification of gaps in actual evaluation methods; (3) and bring recommendation for audits and a system evaluation of the risk and AI impact along the product life cycle, until it is retired.

Training and Education. In relation to the training, it was specifically focused on field and specifically on hospitals. Remarking that workers should have specific training in AI to understand how it works and that its predictions are not always 100% accurate. It was proposed as important to carry out an official training programme in hospitals and define good practices in the adoption of AI in health.

Regulatory Frameworks, and Recommendations. Participants highlight the need that experimental design is complete with the data that feeds AI and certification of adequacy for the data. The necessity of validating methods in different cohorts and designing multidisciplinary teams. The objective would be to analyse and design algorithms with regulations in the impacts on society. Additionally, during the workshop, the teams mentioned that it is important to evaluate the costs and integration of AI-enabled systems within the regulatory frameworks (GLP, GxP) in pharma and life sciences.

Open Data, Transparency, Model Process. Finally, the importance of reproducibility of models was discussed. The need of making tests with statisticians with multivariate patterns. Also, the group discussed the guarantee of the human mechanism in the loop with medical experts in IA applications for healthcare and the explainability, and to be in relation to the AI transparency for the diagnosis and verification by experts in the field.

Challenge E. Awareness: What practical actions are required to raise awareness on the different groups of interest about their rights and responsibilities in the use of AI? Three of the teams analysed the awareness challenge, which defined the following points:

Governance. The governance and the legal aspects of data are key for AI in medicine. Improve awareness on the current AI system, bringing services to help citizenship with AI based applications (also public administration applications).

The groups highlighted the importance of a public debate and control to determine regulations, obligations and transparency about the rights and risks of AI over the population. Also bringing sanctions over the current problems, lack of protection in data and lack of transparency.

Training and Education. One of the most debated points in awareness was education. Multiple options were proposed: making a dynamic AI, demystifying technology in school for inclusion; collaborating with educational systems and including computer skills in primary. This could be formulated with basic AI courses and its impact (based on digital skills and technology accessibility). Teachers would also need to be offered specific training (transversal workshops in universities for data mining, technology, etc.) In this way, globally, it seeks to improve the knowledge of learning analytics and artificial intelligence tools applied to health, administration, legal, politics and other areas.

Citizenship, Participation, Advertising campaigns. Finally, a mentioned aspect for the challenge was to encourage informative campaigns over the rights and responsibilities in the use and application of AI. It was proposed to spread more ethic manuals. It was also mentioned the relevance of improving communication between citizens and science and finding the way to the citizens at the beginning of the development process of AI.

The design of advertising campaigns, not necessarily in regulated educational areas, but implementing jobs in social associations, NGOs, to announce AI benefits in society, raise awareness also in companies and achieve global responsibility.

In the end the best ideas of the workshop could be summarised as:

- Include citizens to the process, design, user experience tests. Develop an AI culture with citizens.
- Open to citizens, explain opportunities, risks, define more strategies with more communication channels with the public.
- Mandatory subventions to diverse teams that guarantee the adequacy of sex and gender to explore the work on R&D.
- Audit and evaluations of risk and AI impact that are done along the lifecycle of the product until its retirement.
- Cost-benefit evaluation of the results, development and research.
- Improve regulation, mandatory transparency. Obligation in the actual legislation.
- Boost data quality, and representativity. Balance teams, samples, and orient investigation over this way.

- Training over bias, knowledge in the educational teams, manuals and training programmes.
- Guarantee the human mechanism in the loop with experts, doctors in artificial intelligence applications for healthcare. AI is more oriented to the people and less to the business.

B4W NETWORKING

E. Workshop: Bioinfo4Women Networking

Additionally, a workshop was designed to empower a collaboration network between different organisations, the invitation was sent to international, national and local organisations that work on topics of gender equality in science, AI, technology and health. The workshop allowed participants to share their needs and present their lines of action. The goal was to generate a channel of international collaboration and support in the interest of bias in sex and gender in artificial intelligence and health.

The session was held virtually on June the 8th 2021 with the participation of 15 institutions and more than 20 women researchers and members of NGOs, international organisations and public national institutions among other members. Within this space, it was mainly sought that every person could give a brief description of their work, highlighting the actions and activities and the needs and requirements that they have.

In the following figure, lines among the different organisations represent possible collaborations. Among the clear actions shown, they were, for example, sharing the design experience of programmes or workshops with new institutions that are proposing new contents or the search and design of projects to obtain shared funding with other projects. The Barcelona Supercomputing Center shared a presentation of existing European and international funding calls.

B4W NETWORKING, 2021. PALAU MACAYA, BARCELONA.

Another aspect identified as necessary was the creation of an active communication channel in Slack, to maintain alive the created relation formed during the session. This channel will enable the organisations to continue

discussing possible collaborations, such as seminars, projects, calls, events, needs, and job offers.

Finally, the B4W announced its mentoring program. It was also possible to specify the development of a shared workshop with Women in BioInformatic & Data Science LA and B4W among the actions specified during the meeting. The evaluation of the session was very positive by participants.

Derived conclusions from the workshop:

- Work in shared project proposals for international calls.
- Disseminate activities among institutions.
- Continue with this kind of initiative to build an international collaboration network.

FINAL CONFERENCE

F. FINAL CONFERENCE

The final conference of the series was held on June 16, 2021, at the Palau Macaya de La Caixa Foundation. The final conference began with the participation of the director of the Palau Macaya Bárbara Palacio, and the subsequent participation of the associate director of the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC), Dr. Josep Maria Martorell.

bioinfo
4women

PROYECTO SELECCIONADO **CONVOCATORIA** PALAU MACAYA **#AIGenderBias**

Actions to overcome current sex and gender bias in science

FINAL CONFERENCE
DATE: **16TH JUNE 2021**
TIME: **6PM to 8PM CEST**
ONLINE English:
<https://bit.ly/3x9SJli>

Josep Maria Martorell
Associate Director at
Barcelona Supercomputing
Center (BSC)

Londa Schiebinger
John L. Hinds Professor
at Stanford University
and Director of the
EU/US Gendered
Innovations

Catherine D'Ignazio
Assistant Professor of
Urban Science &
Planning, Director,
Data+Feminism Lab, MIT

 Fundación "la Caixa"

 Barcelona Supercomputing Center
Centro Nacional de Supercomputación

FINAL CONFERENCE, 2021. PALAU MACAYA, BARCELONA.

The structure of the debate was aimed at presenting the summary of the series by the BSC team, led by María José Rementeria, responsible for the Social Link Analytics unit and the Bioinfo4Women Programme. Moving on to a final discussion with specialists on (1) sex and gender innovations in science, health and medicine, engineering and the environment, and definitions of (2) how to use data and computational methods to work towards racial and gender equity, particularly regarding big data.

Professor Londa Schiebinger, John L. Hinds Professor in History of Science in the Department of History at Stanford University and director of the Gendered Innovations EU / US project in Science, Health, Medicine, Engineering and Environment, began her presentation by introducing the Gendered Innovations programme. She pointed out the importance of integrating the perspective and analysis of sex and gender in the design of the research, being a required element to justify the research and work carried out within the large international organisations, as established in the European Commission Horizon Europe 2020. This aspect is key for the EU, which has funded a team of more than 25 experts. They have published a report with instructions for research and innovation

(Gendered Innovations 2: How Inclusive Analysis Contributes to Research and Innovation, nd).

FINAL CONFERENCE, 2021. PALAU MACAYA, BARCELONA.

The NIH has defined as a mandatory requirement for public funding to introduce the variable sex as a biological variable (SABV). Schiebinger presented different examples of sex and gender biases in different diseases, procedures, in science, health and medicine, engineering and environment research that affect the public. She insisted on the importance of the impact of sex when working with laboratory animals but also other factors (place, sex of the researchers, etc). All these factors could potentially have significant social effects on the results of the experiments.

She also spoke about the differences during COVID-19 for men and women, from the point of view of biological sex, and other factors related to gender and socio-economic aspects.

Thus, the methodology proposed to incorporate sex and gender in the research should consider the different stages in: a. Identification of the problem b. Research design c. Data collection d. Information analysis and finally e. Dissemination of results.

What is Gendered Innovations?

SEX & GENDER ANALYSIS

General Methods
Specific Methods
Terms
Checklists

CASE STUDIES

Science
Health & Medicine
Engineering
Environment

INTERSECTIONAL DESIGN

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

VIDEOS

Print
Tweet
Facebook

ANALYZING SEX

- Report the sex of your subjects, even in single-sex studies
- Report the sex distribution of the cells, animals, or human subjects
- Report how information on sex was obtained
- Disaggregate reported results by sex
- Ensure that sex variations are properly visualized in the tables, figures, and conclusions
- Avoid overgeneralizing sex differences. Are observed sex differences of practical significance? (Moore et al., 2016; Wilkin et al., 2014)
- Report all trends, positive, negative, and non-trends
- Consider following the IACRIF publication guidelines (Harden et al., 2016)

- Sex may play a role in all studies involving human or non-human animals
- Perform a literature review to identify how sex may be of relevance to your study (Moerman et al., 2009)
- Consider whether sex is a variable, confounder, or explanatory variable
- Consider what sex-related characteristics are of relevance to your study (e.g. genetic, physiological, hormonal, anthropometric, biomechanical, injury threshold, levels of pain tolerance, etc.) (Tannenbaum et al., 2019)
- Consider how sex-related factors gender, ethnicity, age, socio-economic status, identity, etc.
- Consider what opportunities have been missed in the past as a result of failing to analyze sex

Open in new tab (PDF) | Download Powerpoint

Related Case Studies

[Animal Research](#)
[Chronic Pain](#)
[Colorectal Cancer](#)
[De-Gendering the Knee](#)
[Dietary Assessment](#)

FINAL CONFERENCE, 2021. PALAU MACAYA, BARCELONA.

Schiebinger pointed out the report published by the Lancet and ICMJE (Schiebinger et al., 2016), which defines as fundamental:

1. Use the terms sex and gender correctly;
2. Inform about the sex and / or gender of the participants;
3. Describe the methods used to determine sex and gender.
4. Separate the report with the data and factors that intersect with sex, such as age
5. Discuss the influence of sex and / or gender on the findings, and
6. Discuss the limitations of the data.

This framework is currently part of a recommendation system, but it is expected that in the future it will be mandatory at the general research level. In addition, it was highlighted the necessity to analyse the intersectional studies that consider variables that interact together such as ethnicity, race, age, socio-economic status, sexuality, language, geographic location, skills, among other key aspects.

Therefore, public policies play an important role in the solutions we seek but must be combined with other actions, such as mandatory support from funding agencies, universities, and also scientific publications that supervise and determine the obligation to represent these variables in the studies. All these aspects should be considered in the evaluations, to develop methods of analysis in sex and gender. This process should generate more rigorous, reproducible analysis and results with better inclusion and transparency.

FINAL CONFERENCE, 2021. PALAU MACAYA, BARCELONA.

Professor Catherine D'Ignazio, Assistant Professor of Urban Science & Planning at MIT and director of the Data + Feminism Lab presented her book *Data Feminism* (D'Ignazio & Klein, 2020). In this published study they highlighted the responsibility of companies and governments in the reproduction of racist and sexist systems. However, when analysing the causes of these reproductions, what we see is not the algorithms, but the society and people that are responsible. In this sense, data feminism is a resistance against the male narratives that circulate and predominate in the population.

Professor D'Ignazio analysed the concept of feminism applied to data, highlighting the importance of intersectional feminism to combat the root of many problems. Equal rights for both genders have not yet been achieved, so it is necessary to acquire a political commitment in this regard. Intersectional feminism is not only about women and gender, it is also about power. Data is power. Intersectional feminism can help revise power, data, and change it by challenging the real causes of biases that reproduce present inequalities.

During her presentation, she mentioned seven principles necessary to apply today by people who work in the area of AI and in the social context to transform present problems defined as:

1. Examine power in different areas, see the interactions between the forces that are reproducing inequalities
2. Challenge power, established schemes,
3. Rethink binarism and hierarchies;
4. Elevate emotion and embodiment
5. Embrace pluralism,
6. Consider context
7. Make work visible.

7 Principles of Data Feminism

Examine power
Challenge power
Rethink binaries and hierarchies
Elevate emotion and embodiment
Embrace pluralism
Consider context
Make labor visible

FINAL CONFERENCE, 2021. PALAU MACAYA, BARCELONA.

This presentation closed the conference series and left room for debates and thought about sex and gender biases in artificial intelligence and health. From the Bioinfo4Women program it is projected:

1. At the political level, a summary will be presented to the responsible in the area of gender and health at the Catalan Parliament to raise the issue and to collaborate in the definition of strategies and public policies.
2. At the research level, work is being done in different European consortia on projects [H2021-01-24: Tackling gender, race and other biases in AI] to develop systems for evaluating sex and gender biases but also to include ethnicity, age, among others variables, in the health area.
3. Finally, at the level of activities to enhance visualization and actions, we are working with ELIXIR, to carry out an upcoming BioHackaton [FAIRX: Quantitative bias assessment in ELIXIR biomedical data resources] in November 2021 to analyze sex data and gender in genomics data repositories in Europe. This will help to understand the existing information, its quality and limitations, and work to define guidelines and recommendations, as well as review the protocols, and the ethical and social aspects of the data.

CONCLUSIONS

CONCLUSIONS

As a result, and conclusions of the debates and reflection sessions, here is a list of proposals:

Public policies and Regulations

Public Policies. AI practitioners, policy-makers and governments should strive to develop guidelines and promote funding research projects focused on health and IA problems related to sex and gender. Furthermore, it is essential to promote, at a scientific level, the regulation in peer-reviewed publications that consider and require this type of analysis with a gender and sex perspective during design, analysis, and results.

In the same way, the need for training on the subject was proposed to public shareholders and funding bodies, to define a scheme that requires projects to consider the perspective of sex and gender. Finally, work on a legal framework that determines the impact and responsibility of the systems that are applied in society.

Education and Training.

Education and training. It is necessary to adapt university study programs to include the discussion about biases, particularly in degrees related to health and engineering, which was discussed to make future professionals aware of the risks and their repercussions. Likewise, the need for training in the field of health, hospitals and related institutions was mentioned, highlighting that health workers must have a clear perspective of the operation and application of AI.

It is important to promote education and awareness about sex and gender biases in schools and institutes, through scientific talks and educational campaigns to promote education in values of equality from childhood. Collaborate with educational systems and include computational skills in primary and secondary education and at the teaching level, spaces for digital transformation, basic AI courses and their impact.

Social Dialogue and Communication. Awareness.

Scientific communication. It is necessary disseminate science and research to citizens to make visible the problems into design and impact of algorithms. To work with multidisciplinary teams and include the issues of bias in the syllabus of university degree curricula and in masters and doctorate training.

Awareness and Dissemination. It is essential to conduct awareness and dissemination campaigns, pointing out the importance of biases in data repositories and the adverse consequences of inequality and proposing alternatives to reduce and eliminate the gap. To develop outreach campaigns in

schools for parents and cultural associations including groups and social movements, as well as young influencers, to reach a wider audience. Additionally, scientific documentaries could show the relevance of historical events in discriminatory clinical practice. Regarding awareness in the clinical part, it was proposed to disseminate information related to the difference of sex and gender regarding the symptoms of diseases for a better diagnosis and treatments. Finally, it is necessary to promote activism from scientific societies and the organization of international campaigns through social networks and the media was considered.

Guidelines. Algorithmic Audits

It is relevant to develop guidelines and recommendations from associations such as Spanish Agency of Medicines and Medical Products (AEMPS), European Medicines Agency (EMA) and The European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations (EFPIA) including the category of sex and gender in the data collection forms. The definition of the terms sex and gender and the need for consensus in their definition was also discussed. It is important to develop a standardised vocabulary approved by the community in scientific studies so that they refer to the same concepts and that are homologous in the different databases and information repositories.

Control and Correction Tools Audit. It is necessary to define metrics to be used by teams of developers to evaluate the models, bias mitigation techniques, and data bias measurement tools and algorithms. It is also important to develop methods to balance databases and have authoring systems that control that the data shown is complete, representative, and not biased. Citizenship must also be included in the design, definition of parameters, analysis and review of results to ensure citizens' rights are protected.

Inclusive Strategies in Healthcare and Biomedical Research

Definition of inclusive strategies in health promotion and care. The sex and gender perspective must be included in the strategies that promote people's health. Design promoting adequate care for people from vulnerable groups such as LGBTIQ+, with special attention to transgender people who are undergoing hormone therapy.

It is essential to consider research from a diversity perspective in medical studies to expand and have intersectional categories of people in health, such as: sex, gender, sexual orientation, ethnicity, nationality, socio-economic status, disability, age. Diversity must be ensured, particularly when using public funding. They also commented on the need to encourage and favour participation in studies from minority groups, encouraging their participation among different actions.

Quality and Fairness. Representativeness

Expansion of Data Collection by diversifying the source, including health data from primary care, sociodemographic studies. Incorporate quality of life data and data

gathered from personal electronic devices. Also, consider gender outside the binary system.

Data quality: Evaluation and Inclusion Criteria. The need to include data evaluation criteria in the publishing policies of scientific journals checking the completeness and balance regarding sex and gender in research data.

Fairness in training data sets. The need for algorithm training data sets not only to have the necessary quality and free of biases was discussed, but also to ensure that they are balanced according to the variables of interest of the problem being addressed. They also commented on the need for a bias catalogue and tools that allow developers to easily identify and correct them.

Review and correct the lack of data in medical studies, completing them with socioeconomic data from various sources. The need to balance the lack of data of those groups that present an inadequate weight in the data sets was debated, using sociodemographic data as possible sources of data to be integrated. In the same way, the need to promote sociological studies and integrate their results with health data and systems.

Multidisciplinary and Inclusive Teams

Multidisciplinary and inclusive development teams. It is necessary to demystify AI and to propose systems that provide answers to unbiased questions and hypotheses. It is considered essential that citizenship participate to the process: the approach, development and verification of results (human- in-the-loop) and the need to form multidisciplinary and inclusive teams of developers to broaden the vision and have critical points of view.

Social Sciences and Humanities. Social and Ethical Impact IA

It was mentioned the necessity to include and work together with Social and Human Sciences, generating additional collaborations that provide key insights to evaluate and enhance the social impact on the public. Importance of integrating different opinions in the design, analysis, development of research to avoid bias and generate audits for citizen participation.

Focus on the social impact of AI in health and in relation to global goals. Connect the work developed in health and AI with the United Nations SDGs to work on global issues where action is needed. Guiding AI with a vision of social good, working in different areas, for example, it was mentioned the possible use to detect violence and domestic abuse, the prediction of malnutrition in vulnerable populations, depression, application of AI to well-being and also in economic, legal, governmental and social or environmental problems.

Trustworthy IA

AI models. AI models need to be revised to analyse and avoid unfair results and classifications and to promote an explainable and trustworthy AI where inconsistencies and bias could be detected. The problem of anonymizing data and protecting privacy in order to have data quality that allows a reproducible study was also discussed.

ANNEXES

04 Annexes

DISSEMINATION

During the series, the dissemination was carried out through different communication channels that were also strengthened by the situation of the COVID-19 pandemic and the context of virtuality.

The main dissemination channel used was the Bioinfo4Women Twitter account with 2.271 followers using the hashtag #AIGenderBias, with supporting coverage by the Barcelona Supercomputing Center Twitter account, which also had 11.400 followers. LinkedIn was used as a second channel to disseminate the series in the Bioinfo4Women profile with 457 followers, and the BSC profile with 13.762 followers. Additionally, more than 1.000 tailored emails in three languages were sent to professionals from different fields who might be interested in the subject. The series was incorporated into the Barcelona Supercomputing Center Newsletter reaching out over 700 employees.

The conferences and seminars were streamed with simultaneous translation in English and Spanish. The videos remain available in the Bioinfo4Women programme website and the Bioinfo4Women Youtube playlist within the Barcelona Supercomputing Center channel.

The videos disseminated in YouTube La Caixa and La Lluçana together with all the materials produced during the sessions, can be found as well in the section of the *Palau Macaya Series: Sex and Gender Bias in Artificial Intelligence and Health* web of the B4W and the YouTube channel of the BSC to preserve and continue with the dissemination of this line of research.

The following details the source links of the series published on the official website of La Caixa Foundation and La Lluçana, entry date June 29, 2021 (increasing figures):

Open Conference - Spanish

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=X9-qn-JifAY&t=2342s>

200 views Fundación la Caixa

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LfHyW-xNDZO>

64 views Fundación la Caixa

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mp2JGJaT8fQ&t=3146s>

288 views La Lluçana

Open Conference - English

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RtOyWxzAnVY>

62 views La Caixa YouTube

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tEWtnldJIn4&t=2379s>

223 views La Lluçana

Seminar Personalized Medicine - Spanish

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=o5puNo0QP4k>

230 views La Lluçana

Seminar Personalized Medicine - English

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Wo23JkLSSwk&t=164s>

171 views La Lluçana

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CMwOErtO_Dc

88 views Fundació la Caixa

Seminar Ethics & Society IA - Spanish

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OC9YEWuREA>

195 views Fundació la Caixa

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cvYW-Cfnyiw&t=1142s>

273 views La Lluçana

Seminar Ethics & Society - English

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LR1FihjBKro&t=16s>

88 views La Lluçana

Final Conference - Spanish

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DrdfS3dSNf4>

57** views Fundació la Caixa

(**Information from La Caixa Report)

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_iTpA_m8hk0

19 views Bioinfo4Women Programme Website

Final Conference - English

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PVfSEFI1kHo>

64** views Fundació la Caixa

(**Information from La Caixa Report)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=x24ju8tulwg>

18 views Bioinfo4Women Programme Website

In addition to the organisation of Bioinfo4Women, La Caixa Foundation through La Chincheta facilitated an interview to Dr. Carme Valls, keynote speaker of the session "Sex and gender biases in Health" published in Univaris of Medscape as of March 30, 2021.

<https://www.univadis.es/viewarticle/entrevista-a-car-me-valls-lloret-medicina-con-perspectiva-de-genero-741337>

María José Rementería, leader of the Social Link Analytics group of the Life Sciences Department of the BSC was interviewed on April 1, 2021 in the radio show El Matí of Catalunya Ràdio introducing the series and the topics tackled, as well as the the Bioinfo4Women activities. The audio can be found in the web:

<https://www.ccma.cat/catradio/alacarta/el-mati-de-catalunya-radio/el-biaix-de-genero-i-sexe-de-la-intelligencia-artificial/audio/1097392/>. Rementería was interviewed as well in the digital media Innovaspain.
<https://www.innovaspain.com/bioinfo4women-maria-jose-rementeria/>

For each workshop and / or conference and / or seminar:

- A report that summarises the scientific references and training that has been prepared by the facilitator of each workshop based on the debate organised in the seminars.
- Interviews in public newspapers with Dr. Carme Valls and María José Rementería.
- In the 4 sessions open to the public, Twitter surveys were conducted at the end of the streaming to gather the interest in the subject, relevance, involvement and usefulness of their work. And in the 3 closed workshops, surveys designed in Google Forms were carried out and sent to participants by email.
- The content of the project will be available in a section of the official B4W website. All the information has been translated into English to boost visibility and diversity: <http://bioinfo4women.bsc.es>

The Social Observatory

A place for *debate* and *reflection*

Sex and Gender Bias in Artificial Intelligence and Health: Building a Future for Equality

Our challenge

Enable an open discussion, exchange knowledge and analyze the social, ethical and technological challenges of gender and sex bias in health, personalized medicine and artificial intelligence (AI) research.

Our goal

Provide information and scientific evidence on the importance of sex and gender bias in science and more specifically in the fields of health, personalized medicine and artificial intelligence (AI). The ultimate goal is to apply innovative solutions to reduce bias.

SELECTED PROJECT PALAU MACAYA CALL

Coorganized with: Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)

#GenderBias #GenderAI #GenderDataScience
#GenderEquality #PalauMacaya

From Tuesday
March 16th to
Wednesday June
16th 2021

Pg. de Sant Joan, 108
Barcelona

Sex and Gender Bias in Artificial Intelligence and Health: Building a Future for Equality

Our work dynamics

The Bioinfo4Women Programme of the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)'s Life Sciences Department will coordinate the series. The series is structured on two main themes: (1) personalized medicine and (2) artificial intelligence. Each theme will include different activities: seminar, working group and participatory workshop. The goal of these activities is to allow and encourage discussion between scientists and prominent representatives from different fields (business, media, NGOs, research institutes and public administration, among others) and to raise awareness about sex and gender bias in health and about the risk of amplifying and perpetuating bias through artificial intelligence.

ACTIVITIES

The program is subject to the current sanitary situation and may change to accommodate new restrictions.

OPENING CONFERENCE | MARCH 16TH, FROM 18 TO 20H CET

Sex and gender bias in artificial intelligence and health

The opening conference will define the goals of the series by enabling an open discussion with international experts to analyze the implications sex and gender bias has on the development of new technologies in health and personalized medicine, with a particular focus on the risk of amplifying and perpetuating bias through artificial intelligence.

ONSITE (REGISTRATION REQUIRED) AND ONLINE
Check the event on our website.

BY:

Presenters: **María José Rementería & Nataly Buslón**, Social Link Analytics, Bioinfo4women Programme, Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC).

Alfonso Valencia, ICREA Research Professor, Life Sciences Department Director at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) and Director of the Spanish National Bioinformatics Institute (INB-ISCIII). **María Teresa Ferretti**, Co-founder and chief scientific officer, Women's Brain Project (WBP).

SEMINAR | APRIL 14TH, FROM 10 TO 13H CET

Sex and Gender perspective in the future of personalized Medicine

Personalized Medicine proposes a new paradigm by which therapeutic decisions are made considering the individual characteristics of patients. Scientific evidence proves that there are individual differences in the response to drugs due to not only genetic factors, but also intrinsic factors, such as biological sex and gender. Biomedical research needs to include sex and gender differences to predict variability in therapeutic response, avoid side effects or reduced drug efficacy, and determine disease prognosis in all professional health activities, from the experimental and technological development to ethics and law.

ONSITE (REGISTRATION REQUIRED) AND ONLINE
Check the event on our website.

BY:

Luis Rocha, Professor and director of the NSF-NRT Complex Networks and Systems graduate Program in Informatics, member of the Indiana University Network Science Institute, and core faculty of the Cognitive Science Program at Indiana University, Bloomington, USA. **Carme Valls**, Politician and physician specialised in endocrinology with a gender perspective. Director of the "Women, Health and Quality of Life" program at the Center for Health Analysis and Programs CAPS. **Silvina Catuara Solarz**, Ph.D., Project evaluator and a mentor of start-ups at EIT Health, Member of the WHO Digital Health Roster of Experts, Lead in Technology Application for Neuroscience and Mental Health, Women's Brain Project Moderator: **Davide Cirillo**, PostDoctoral Researcher at the Computational Biologist group, Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC).

SELECTED PROJECT PALAU MACAYA CALL

#GenderBias #GenderAI #GenderDataScience
#GenderEquality #PalauMacaya

WORKING GROUP | APRIL 14TH, FROM 14 TO 18H CET

Building a Future for Equality: Challenges and strategies in Personalized Medicine

Analysis of the application of sex and gender perspective to scientific research in health and personalized medicine. We will think about tools and strategies to improve the current bias in health using innovative tools to reduce bias and improve the population's quality of life.

CLOSED MEETING

SEMINAR | MAY 11TH, FROM 10 TO 13 H CET

Social, Ethical and Technical challenges of sex and gender bias in AI and healthcare

AI bias is present in algorithms in different ways, from experimental design, the data collected or used to train the algorithm, and finally the interpretation of the outcomes. As a result, it can create unfair decisions, generating discrimination or stigmatization towards certain groups of people. Part of this bias is inherited from historic or socially-constructed biases. AI can help identify and reduce these biases, but it can also enlarge the problem of inclusion and diversity if they are not embedded throughout the entire AI's system life cycle. An open and multidisciplinary dialogue is needed to include a gender perspective to the design and deployment of AI in healthcare in order to promote fairness and trustworthiness to society.

ONSITE (REGISTRATION REQUIRED) AND ONLINE
Check the event on our website.

BY:

Karina Gibert, professor at UPC, co-founder and director at IDEAI-UPC, Vicepresident of Equity and Ethics at COEINF.
Itziar de Lecuona, Associate Professor at School of Medicine (UB) & Assistant Director Bioethics and Law Observatory-UNESCO Chair in Bioethics. **Paula Petrone**, Founder and Managing Director at Phenobyte
Moderator: **Atia Cortés**, PostDoctoral Researcher at the Social Link Analytics unit, Barcelona Supercomputing Center (RSC).

WORKING GROUP | MAY 11TH, FROM 14 TO 18 H CET

Building a Future for Equality: Route map towards an inclusive AI for a better healthcare system

Scientific analysis of sex and gender bias in new technologies and artificial intelligence and the risk of amplifying and consolidating bias. We will work on proposals to define strategies and possible solutions tackling the problem from a diverse and inclusive point of view on social, ethical and technological challenges.

CLOSED MEETING

WORKING GROUP | MAY 12TH, FROM 16 TO 20 H

Women in Science International Network: Health and Artificial Intelligence

Debate with different organizations and social initiatives working on sex and gender bias in health and artificial intelligence to define specific actions to generate and maintain an international collaborative support network.

CLOSED MEETING

SELECTED PROJECT PALAU MACAYA CALL

#GenderBias #GenderAI #GenderDataScience
#GenderEquality #PalauMacaya

CONFERENCE | JUNE 16TH, FROM 16 TO 20 H

Actions to overcome current sex and gender bias in science

Final debate with international experts on (1) sex and gender innovations in science, health and medicine, engineering and environment, and definitions of (2) how to use data and computational methods to work towards racial and gender equality. This is the closing conference of the series, and will include a presentation of the results and a proposal of measures to be applied in the future for the benefit of society as a whole.

ONSITE (REGISTRATION REQUIRED) AND ONLINE
Check the event on our website.

BY:

Presenters: **María José Rementería & Nataly Buslón.**

Social Link Analytics, Bioinfo4women Programme, Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC).

Josep Maria Martorell Rodon, Associate Director at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC). **Londa Schiebinger**, John L. Hinds Professor of History of Science in the History Department at Stanford University and Director of the EU/US Gendered Innovations in Science, Health & Medicine, Engineering, and Environment Project. **Catherine D'Ignazio**, Assistant Professor of Urban Science and Planning in the Department of Urban Studies and Planning at MIT. Director of the Data + Feminism Lab.

"la Caixa" Foundation

SPEAKERS CONFERENCE SEMINAR, WORKSHOPS, THE B4W TEAM

Speakers (chronological order)

- **Zulema Altamirano**, Directora de la Unidad de Mujeres y Ciencia. Ministerio Ciencia e Innovación, España.
- **Laura Perez**, Tinenta d'Alcaldia Drets Socials, Justícia Global, Feminismes i LGTBI · Ajuntament de Barcelona.
- **Alfonso Valencia**, Barcelona Supercomputing Center. Life Sciences Department Director.
- **Maria Teresa Ferretti**, Co-founder and Chief Scientific Officer, Women's Brain Project.
- **Carme Valls Llobet**, Directora Mujer, Salud y Calidad de Vida» en el Centro de Análisis y Programas Sanitarios (CAPS).
- **Valeria Raparelli**, University of Alberta, Canadá, University of Ferrara, Italia.
- **Luis Rocha**, Director of the NFS-NRT. Indiana University. USA
- **Silvina Catuara**, European Institute of Innovation and Technology Health (EIT Health).
- **Karina Gibert**, Catedrática UPC & Vicedegana Igualdad y Ética COEINF.
- **Itziar de Lecuona**, Directora Observatoria Bioética y Derecho - Cátedra UNESCO.
- **Allison Gardner**, Keele University & Women Leading in Artificial Intelligence.
- **Paula Petrone**, SGlobal. Managing Director de Phenobyte.
- **Josep Maria Martorell**, Barcelona Supercomputing Center, Director Asociado.
- **Londa Schiebinger** Stanford University. Director, EU/US Gendered Innovations in Science, Health & Medicine.
- **Catherine D'Ignazio**, MIT. Department of Urban Studies & Planning. Director, Data + Feminism Lab.

Workshops Participants (alphabetical order)

Ainhoa Flecha; Allison Gardner; Alba Jené; Anais Baudot; Ana Dueso; Alfredo Vellido; Ana Brugulat; Ana Julia Velez Rueda; Beatriz Villarejo; Begum Genc; Bhuvana Meenakshi; Carme Valls Llobet; Carla Conejo; Carlos Sierra; Concepción Sanz; Cristian Barrue; Cristina Clos; Eduard Porta; Eider Arenaza- Urquijo; Elena Carreras; Esther Paniagua; Emilia López-Iñesta; Enzo Ferrante; Ester Bonet; Fouzia Radouani; Francisco García; Gemma Galdon Clavell; Isabelle Vernos; Jayne Hope; Karma Peiró; Karina Gibert; Kerstin Bach; Laia Subirat; Lucía Tróchez Ardila; Lucy Jiménez; Lydia González; Maite Paramio; María Del Pilar Oller; Marjolein Oorsprong; Mercedes Jorquera; Natalie Cernecka; Natasa Milic-Frayling; Nieves Lorenzo; Nuria Castells; Nuria Agell; Osnat Hakimi; Oriol Rios; Paula Petrone; Rocio Garcia; Rosana Corram; Roberto Confalonieri; Sarah Bonnin; Sara Pedraz; Simona Giardina; Shalini Kurapati; Teresa Riera; Teresa scantamburlo; Trinidad Serrano Aulló; Ute Roehrig; Vera Pancaldi; Victoria Prieto.

Team Collaboration:

- **Atia Cortés**, Postdoctoral Researcher, Barcelona Supercomputing Center. Programa Bioinfo4Women.
- **Davide Cirillio**, Postdoctoral Researcher, Barcelona Supercomputing Center. Programa Bioinfo4Women.
- **Eva Navarrete**, Asistente Director Life Science Department en el Barcelona Supercomputing Center. Programa Bioinfo4Women.
- **Eva Alloza**, Training and Support Officer en el Barcelona Supercomputing Center. Programa Bioinfo4Women.
- **Teia Guix Boqué**, Co-emprèn.
- **Esther Bernado**, Co-emprèn.
- **Irene Lapuente Aguilar**, La Mandarina de Newton.
- **Yolanda Altmiras Delgado**, Fundación “la Caixa” – Palau Macaya.
- **Jordi Gaya**, Focus. Fundación “la Caixa” – Palau Macaya.

Project Director:

- **María José Rementeria**, Team Leader Social Link Analytics, Barcelona Supercomputing Center. Programa Bioinfo4Women.
- **Nataly Buslón**, Postdoctoral Researcher, Barcelona Supercomputing Center. Programa Bioinfo4Women.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Arnegard, M. E., Whitten, L. A., Hunter, C., & Clayton, J. A. (2020). Sex as a Biological Variable: A 5-Year Progress Report and Call to Action. *Journal of Women's Health (2002)*, 29(6), 858–864. <https://doi.org/10.1089/jwh.2019.8247>
- Cirillo, D., Catuara-Solarz, S., Morey, C., Guney, E., Subirats, L., Mellino, S., Gigante, A., Valencia, A., Rementeria, M. J., Chadha, A. S., & Mavridis, N. (2020). Sex and gender differences and biases in artificial intelligence for biomedicine and healthcare. *Npj Digital Medicine*, 3(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-020-0288-5>
- D'Ignazio, C., & Klein, L. F. (2020). *Data feminism*. <https://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&scope=site&db=nlebk&db=nlabk&AN=2378911>
- Gender and women's mental health*. (n.d.). Retrieved 27 July 2021, from <https://www.who.int/teams/control-of-neglected-tropical-diseases/yaws/diagnosis-and-treatment/mental-health-and-substances-use>
- Gendered Innovations 2: How Inclusive Analysis Contributes to Research and Innovation*. (n.d.). 244.
- Grogan, K. E. (2019). How the entire scientific community can confront gender bias in the workplace. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 3(1), 3–6. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-018-0747-4>
- Ibrahim, H., Liu, X., Zariffa, N., Morris, A. D., & Denniston, A. K. (2021). Health data poverty: An assailable barrier to equitable digital health care. *The Lancet Digital Health*, 3(4), e260–e265. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500\(20\)30317-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500(20)30317-4)
- Lecuona, I. de (coord). (n.d.). *Pautes per avaluar projectes de recerca i innovació en salut que utilitzin tecnologies emergents i dades personals*. 83.
- McLaughlin, J.E., Wolcott, M., Hubbard, D. et al. A qualitative review of the design thinking framework in health professions education. *BMC Med Educ* 19, 98 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-019-1528-8>
- Objetivos y metas de desarrollo sostenible – Desarrollo Sostenible*. (n.d.). Retrieved 27 July 2021, from <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/es/objetivos-de-desarrollo-sostenible/>
- Oldfield, M., Gardner, A., Smith, A. L., Steventon, A., & Coughlan, E. (2021, June 2). *Ethical funding for trustworthy AI: Initial workshop outcomes*. AISB

Symposium 2021.

[https://researchportal.port.ac.uk/portal/en/publications/ethical-funding-for-trustworthy-ai-initial-workshop-outcomes\(4d544e68-2f4d-4cf2-b670-9cb161bd97bd\).html](https://researchportal.port.ac.uk/portal/en/publications/ethical-funding-for-trustworthy-ai-initial-workshop-outcomes(4d544e68-2f4d-4cf2-b670-9cb161bd97bd).html)

Principled Artificial Intelligence | Berkman Klein Center. (2020, May 2).

<https://cyber.harvard.edu/publication/2020/principled-ai>

Schiebinger, L., Leopold, S. S., & Miller, V. M. (2016). Editorial policies for sex and gender analysis. *The Lancet*, 388(10062), 2841–2842.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(16\)32392-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(16)32392-3)

Schiebinger, L., & Schraudner, M. (2011). Interdisciplinary Approaches to Achieving Gendered Innovations in Science, Medicine, and Engineering1.

Interdisciplinary Science Reviews, 36(2), 154–167.

<https://doi.org/10.1179/030801811X13013181961518>

UNESCO. (2019). *Women in Science* (p. 4).

<http://uis.unesco.org/sites/default/files/documents/fs55-women-in-science-2019-en.pdf>

United Nations S. (2020). *Visualizar los datos: La representación de las mujeres en la sociedad*. ONU Mujeres. <https://www.unwomen.org/digital-library/multimedia/2020/2/infographic-visualizing-the-data-womens-representation>

Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. *The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship*. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016).

<https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>